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SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK FOR THE CARE COLLECTION

1. Introduction

The CARE collection is an open panel of well characterized zoonotic and foodborne bacterial strains

Microbiological Reference materials (RMs) are perfectly characterized microbial strains that are essential components for quality control, validation of new methods, proficiency testing (PT) and the advancement of science. The CARE joint integrative project aims to create a collection of foodborne pathogenic bacterial strains easily findable and accessible that can be used as RMs.

A list of seven major bacterial species: *Listeria monocytogenes* / *Staphylococcus aureus* / *Yersinia* sp. / *Salmonella enterica* subsp *enterica* / *Campylobacter* sp. / *Bacillus* sp. / *Escherichia coli*, and a set of traceability criteria and characteristics were established by expert panels to qualify strains for the CARE collection. The microbiological resources of the CARE collection originate from the collections of the CARE consortium. A database associated with a web portal has been created offering search, order and strains deposit functionalities.

Importantly, the physical CARE collection will be maintained, stored and made accessible under certified quality standards via three microbial Biological Resource Centers (mBRCs): BVR (IZSLER), CIRM-BP (INRAE) and CIP (IP), members of the One Health EJP consortium. The maintenance of the physical collection by mBRCs supported on the long-term by their institutions is a guarantee of sustainability.

Each RM of the CARE collection is associated with metadata about its origin, relevant phenotypic (including antimicrobial resistance profile) characteristics and genomic information. All CARE catalog entries are Nagoya compliant and their integration into the mBRCs catalogs (*i.e.*, available in BRCs) is underway.

The implementation of the CARE catalog is a joint effort of 15 European veterinary, food safety and public health agencies, universities and research institutes among which 6 EURLs. This unique initiative to collect and share food safety related zoonotic RMs isolated from humans, animals, food or the environment will enhance the harmonization of scientific activities within the European public health sector.

2. The sustainability plan of the CARE collection and its associated catalog

The sustainability plan was established following a sustainability framework (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The sustainability framework for the CARE collection and its catalog defines the vision and strategy, the sustainability goals and objectives. (We probably need a reference for this framework – company ?)

2.1. Sustained Impact

The expected impact of the CARE collection is to Improve quality control, validation of new methods, proficiency testing (PT) and advancement of science in the foodborne pathogen sector.

2.2. Sustained behaviors and service utilization

We wish to encourage a systematic and routine use of the CARE catalog of microbiological resources by European agencies active in the One Health sector.

3. Level 1: Upstream requirements for sustainability

3.1. Sustained resources

Human and financial resources are sufficient in mBRCs agencies to maintain and update the CARE catalog and its information system. The CARE catalog represents only a fraction of the collection of the 3 mBRCs. It should be noted, however, that the acquisition of new resources by BRCs is limited in volume and per year (approx. 200/year in total), so the expansion of the CARE catalogue has physical limits that cannot be exceeded unless additional human resources are provided through specific dedicated tasks in future projects.

3.2. Sustained Capacity

The Characterization/Conservation/Distribution of microbiological resources is a mission of mBRCs which beneficiaries as mentioned in the introduction of the full support of their parent institutions.

3.3. Sustained Motivation

The motivation of end-users of the CARE collection will be dependent upon:
The full availability on the short-term of the CARE collection to improve harmonization among veterinary and public health agencies for method development and for research purposes. This requires a rapid inclusion of the strains in the CARE collection, which means that all the deposit documents must be rapidly signed by the authorities to which the strain providers belong.

On the mid-term, and in line with the quality management systems under which the mBRCs operate, a continuous quantitative and qualitative improvement of the content of the CARE collection and of its associated services including information associated to strains.

3.4. Sustained Linkages

The links that will sustain the collection in the long term can be divided between links within the historical CARE partners, with European public health agencies and the numerous initiatives in the One Health sector.

The three years of the CARE project have built a community between BRCs and veterinary, food safety and public health agencies that recognize the value of openly sharing sets of well-characterised and regulatory compliant strains that will enable harmonization of practices. The links within this community need to be maintained and expanded to include new partners. To do so, it is important to maintain the activity of the expert groups which will remain vigilant to the inclusion of new strains resulting from their work and from the epidemiological and scientific watch.

The project has also allowed to build new links between mBRCs that are now co-responsible of a common collection. The setting up of annual meetings to review the state of the collection and its characterisation will help to maintain these links to keep high the standards of the CARE catalog.

There are 6 EURLs among the CARE consortium that will advertise and keep informed EFSA of the development of the CARE initiative.

The Med-Vet-Net network of excellence that bring together expertise in the veterinary science, public health and food research at European level and on which the EJP-OH was built is a major asset to help establish the initiative in the long term. Many initiatives are being taken at the overarching OH-EJP level (Inventory

and outcome documents, DMPs, dissemination workshop, Simulation exercises, targeted reports, stakeholder conferences, policy events) which can benefit the CARE collection.

The 3 mBRCs are members of the pan-European Microbiological Resources Research Infrastructure (MIRRI; <https://www.mirri.org/>) which was recently established as an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) and recognized as such by ESFRI as a major asset for European research. MIRRI will provide additional visibility and project opportunities for CARE.

4. Level 2: Downstream requirements for sustainability

4.1. Sustained Service delivery

Update the CARE physical catalog to make it representative of the circulating microbiological hazards and filling the needs of research and development needs in the food safety sector. Public/unique health agencies should continue to be encouraged to make visible and share certain key microbiological resources that are relevant and identified as such by the expert panels.

A validation procedure of new entries for updating the CARE catalog must be maintained on the long-term, requiring to keep alive the CARE expert panels.

The CARE collection and the distribution of microbiological resources must be maintained on the long-term. The choice made in the CARE project to entrust three long-established mBRCs well supported by their parent institutions, represents a strong guarantee for the sustainability of these activities.

4.2. Sustained Access

DB and Web portal have to be maintained and timely updated to provide the expected services. The choice made in the CARE project to use an integrated commercial software system, used by one of the BRCs for its own resources and bringing together all the information of the CARE collection is a guarantee of sustainability. The DMP indicates that if the partnership ends, the company undertakes to return all the data in open format (json/csv/Excel/MySQL/MongoDB) or any other format for export to another database (with architecture diagram).

4.3. Sustained demand

To sustain the demand, it is essential that the relevant scientific and public health communities are well aware of the CARE collection and how to access it. The communication strategy to be implemented will include publication describing the collection, its associated data and information system, datapaper and communication in the culture collection, microbiological and public health scientific meetings. It is also germane to mention that the three mBRCs are members of the MIRRI european research infrastructure on microbiological resources that will ensure an increased visibility of the resources

An important aspect is that pricing is fairly established and well accepted by users. The fees currently set were established on the basis of the usual prices charged by the mCRBs for their collection. This pricing is particularly fair since CARE strains are associated with a lot of information that is not commonly available.

To conclude, the sustainability of the CARE collection and its online catalog is built on solid foundation. Efforts will need to be maintained over the long term to ensure the visibility of this resource and to ensure that it meets the needs of the One-health community.